

REGARDING THE LEGITIMACY OF JUDICIAL SUPREMACY IN EXERCISING CONSTITUTIONAL REVIEW (DEFENSE AND CRITICISMS)

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Fabiano Cândido de Oliveira

*Bachelor's degree in Legal and Social Sciences (Law – Presidente Antônio Carlos University
– Aimorés Campus - MG). Email: fco1974mg@gmail.com*

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*Bachelor's degree in Political Science (UNINTER). Undergraduate student in International
Relations – MULTIVIX. Post-Doctorate in Psychology. Email:
srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.*

ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the issue of the legitimacy of judicial supremacy in the exercise of constitutionality control, presenting a defense and also some criticisms. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it brings to the field of investigative debate an issue that remains pending and that does not clarify the real function of the Supreme Court with regard to the constitutional principle within a democratic regime. Its social relevance is of the highest and absolute interest, because it makes it possible to clarify to the general public the role and scope of action of the Supreme Court justices in relation to the protection of the law and the Constitution. This is a bibliographical essay, based on analytical thinking originating from political science and social psychology. The discussion about this judicial legitimacy in the control of constitutionality is, per se, a sociological aberration, because no power is granted the exercise of control by the Magna Carta, an expression that can be interpreted as manipulation of the law according to private intentions to the detriment of the public interest. The conclusions reached are that the constitution of a country and its entire retina of laws and legal and moral norms are within the scope of the letter of the law, and should be transparent, objective, direct, and do away with intermediaries who seek to give it the meaning that best suits them. The mere fact that someone files a lawsuit with the Supreme Court seeking an interpretation of the constitutional legal text should already be considered a crime against the Constitution, and the judges should already deny the request without any right to assess the merits of the representation itself.

Keywords: Federal Constitution. Exercise of constitutionality control. Democratic regime.

INTRODUCTION

Democracies, in order to exist and persist as such, require a legal code, created from their legitimate and customary characteristics, aimed at protecting individuals, the Nation, National Heritage, and social well-being, guaranteeing to all, without distinction, the legal security to which they are entitled. This document is called the Constitution, produced and legitimized at the federal level, which already defines its sovereign power; that is, no law in the country can be created without being subordinate to its legal power.

In this sense, political actions do not always tend to obey such limits, which gives rise to questions about the constitutionality of the proposal presented and, once any action in this regard is filed, it becomes *necessary* for the Judiciary to be called upon in order to resolve doubts regarding the representation in question and, what is most striking is the ease with which the constitutional principle is violated, according to the abject interests of each ideological group that proposes to seize power, disguising it under the euphemistic demagogic discourse of guardian and protector of Democracy.

The fact that there is a need for a body to mediate and interpret constitutional laws already reveals that they are not natural and, paradoxically, democracy allows its participants to extrapolate certain precepts. James Frazer (1854-1941) states that rules only exist to control what nature itself does not instinctively control, as a way to preserve individual and collective life. However, the integral and proper protection of the constitutional principle, guaranteeing the legal security of a country, is a way to avoid both tyranny and anarchy. Thus, the first major question to consider and address in an argument weighing the judgment on the constitutionality of a country is to determine who, in fact, holds the right of supremacy as guardian of the constitutional principle. Following this line of thought, *who is granted legitimacy with regard to judicial supremacy in relation to the control of constitutionality?* This is a legal-constitutional euphemism, based on the simple fact that the body that drafts the Magna Carta of a democratic country is the legislative branch, the one that represents the people; therefore, the legitimacy of judicial supremacy represents a state of precariousness, not a sovereign power *ad aeternum*.

This condition arises because laws are, *broadly speaking*, products of sociological mutations and transmutations caused by the advancement of thought and the existential conditions to which the population is subjected, such as the growth of economic power, population increase, and changes in forms of commercial and service relations. This means that the jurisprudence and *corpus legis* of a nation are always under analysis, being subjected to

untimely interpretations, in order to determine how much they contemplate and guarantee citizens the power to fully exercise their subjective public right.

Nietzsche (2007) states that democracy is the government of the weak and, therefore, to protect those less rapacious individuals, who do not have the power to defend themselves against the stronger ones, laws are created that keep everyone under the custody of fragility. However, these need to be safeguarded, because the wild and primitive spirit of the species from which it originates still lives, scratching at the walls of the cell in which it is imprisoned. This behavior has been given the name instinct, and Freud clarifies that, "an instinct would be an impulse, present in every living organism, tending to the restoration of a previous state, which this living being had to abandon due to the influence of disturbing external forces, a kind of organic elasticity or, if you prefer, the expression of the inertia of organic life" (Freud, [1920] 2006, p. 28-9).

When legal power, as it was the precursor to the Roman model and, by extension, the model for the construction of the Brazilian system, was intended to maintain equanimity [*conceived under a conceptual model of harmonious balance*] between natural law, customary law, and political law [*positivist*]. It is in this sense that the people, through their legitimately elected representatives, grant power to the Judiciary, with the intention that the conceptual judgment of the Most Serene Goddess of Wisdom Pallas Athena be preserved in the conscience of the judges occupying the office.

This is what the Athenian Goddess proclaims:

Hear now what I decree, citizens of Athens, you who judge the first cause of bloodshed. Henceforth the people of Aegeus shall preserve this Council of Judges, ever renewed, on this Hill of Ares. Neither anarchy nor despotism, this is the rule which I advise my citizens to observe with respect. If you respect, as is fitting, this august Institution, you will have in it a bulwark for the country, salvation for the City. Incorruptible, venerable, inflexible, such is the Tribunal which I here institute to watch, ever awake, over the sleeping City (Euripides. *The Eumenides* [485 BC - verses 681-706], quoted by Souza, 1987, pp. 29-30).

What is expressed in the Magistrate's words is sobriety, reasonableness, and the course to be followed by the Judiciary, determining the path to Athenian Democracy, which would extend throughout *almost* the entire Western world from then on. His discourse does not use the expression "supremacy," but rather *strict adherence* to the principles of governance and preservation of peace, requiring intervention when necessary to exert its clarifying force regarding the rights and duties incumbent upon each citizen and each entity. However, if this precept is safeguarded to this day as a supreme and *sui generis principle* of constitutional law,

this alone is sufficient to clarify why there is no harmony between the branches of power; there is a state of conflict such that the maintenance of order is achieved through legal doctrine and the power conferred upon the judge who acts as an arbitrator when confrontations occur, in which both parties consider themselves to be in the domain of reason, that is, what is at stake is not a right and a duty; But the absolute intent is to make two rights prevail: the right to exercise tyranny and the right to impose one's will through anarchy; a situation that inevitably leads to revolutions, according to the thought of F. Hegel (1770-1831).

The emblematic, problematic, and enigmatic concept of democracy.

When considering a particular problem, it's always necessary to clarify that *a problem only becomes a problem when it *turns* into a problem* . In other words, in the field of science, the interest in unraveling a phenomenon arises when its existence begins to harm social order and negatively interfere with human development. With the issue of democracy, this shouldn't be a problem, because its very nature guarantees the maintenance of a certain level of imbalance between the parties, without compromising the persistence of life in social equanimity. This condition shouldn't be confused with harmony, because then we would no longer be living under a democratic regime. Democratic coexistence presupposes the existence of conflicts, and the search for their resolution guarantees the advancement and deepening of thought, leading to a broader understanding of the issue.

Since the emergence of democracy in the city of Athens (Greece), still in Antiquity, its existence and persistence have not pleased those who wished to assume power and who, for unknown reasons, were not led to do so. This gave rise to all kinds of criticism against the regime and, even though it was practically abolished from Western cultures for an extended period, the idea persisted and, with the advent of the rise of the bourgeoisie and in its wake, the occurrence of the Industrial Revolution, which gave rise to the capitalist financial system, the idea of democracy returned to the interests of political systems, not without the existence of groups nostalgic for the times of imperial and monarchical rule who did not fight for its end.

When it is argued here that democracy is an emblematic concept, it refers to a vision of it in which its evocation presupposes broad freedom of expression, respecting contemporary social rights, where the right of each extends only as far as the right of others allows; that is, it is marked by mutual and reciprocal rights and duties; however, these are always conflicting because the interests are of a particular nature. This characteristic of divergence in the judgment of things is what makes it so unique, and even the State is not responsible for promoting the

well-being of all, but rather of the majority, through public policies that best meet the needs of individuals, seen and interpreted as a social body.

This condition of freedom upon which the concept of democracy is built and grounded bothers some individuals, whether due to hidden interests or a constructed narcissistic vision that consolidates itself as it is forced to analyze hidden causes based on even more bizarre interests. In other words, an aristocratic, oligarchic, and plutocratic elite is forming, considering themselves superior individuals simply because they managed to cure themselves of the cursed disease called guilt implanted in the human spirit with the creation of democracy. Strangely, this did not make them stronger; only less susceptible to being attacked by despicable and emasculating feelings such as remorse, guilt, conscience, and regret. Absent all these feelings from human thought, what remains is no longer a democracy, and even the State, when called *democratic*, is endowed with an organism that seeks to keep all these elements alive within its state, so that it does not lose its identity.

To assert that the concept of democracy is problematic stems from the fact that many confuse the freedom afforded by the regime with the idea of being able to do whatever one pleases, without having to respect the limits of ethics and social coexistence. Being free presupposes respect for the principles governed by the social contract, contrary to what one might think of doing what one understands as something subject to deliberate will. This already falls within the realm of a society in which the understanding of laws and norms is not transparent.

Finally, the concept of democracy is enigmatic because when the Serene Goddess of Wisdom, Pallas Athena, says that there should be neither tyranny nor anarchy, it is because she already knew beforehand that these two types of abuses would occur [*and were not merely subject to occasional occurrences*]; which, in the same way, presumes that it is the right of the State to use brute force when necessary and, in the same proportion, it is the right of the people to rise up against the Power when they feel wronged in their legitimately constituted rights. In this, it would be up to the Judiciary to act as a moderating agent, seeking equity between the parties, obliging each to assume their responsibilities as provided by law.

It is based on this very special and difficult-to-control condition that the State, since its creation, has produced a set of laws, organized in a single document, which it titled the Sovereign Constitution. This constitution regulates all social life, and every law, governmental action, and public policy must be subject to its value judgment, prescribed in its pages, in such a way determined by legal transparency that its understanding would not require interpreters.

What needs to be clarified is that the Constitution of any nation cannot afford the extravagant luxury of having someone or a group of scholars who prove capable of interpreting its legal guidelines because, by engaging in this process, one ceases to have a legal document and becomes faced with an oracular revelation, a dubious expression of what should be obvious and not express any kind of ambiguity. Thus, the Constitution of a nation must be obvious, transparent, objective, direct, and concise. Any dimension outside this scope would render such an object susceptible to manipulation by groups that live in a devious manner. The mere fact that, in a democracy, there is even one individual who defines himself as capable of deciphering constitutional ordinances already leaves open the possibility that many others will use the same right and give a different interpretation to the same document and its legal scope, which gives rise to incongruities and unsolvable conflicts, allowing the birth of an anarchic state within the democratic rule of law itself, which corrodes its power to such an extent that, in the end, what remains is a state held hostage by the very laws it constructed in order to maintain order and avoid political chaos.

It so happened that, throughout the process of the return of democracy within the Brazilian State, precepts were created where circumspect groups, unable to see their decisions heeded according to their particular and singular desires, created an alternative path, where the judiciary came to be seen as a supremacy independent of any superior judgment and its decisions ceased to be enlightening, becoming dictatorial. With this, this power was transformed into a mechanism of anarchic control, using for this purpose the legal instrument that should protect it, at the cost of its own existence.

What the Constitution of a democratic nation resolves is to grant power to the Judiciary so that, ultimately, after all valid appeals have been exhausted, recourse is made to it in search of clarification regarding the matter at hand and the laws governing it, a condition under which it can in no way determine the end of the litigious issue. In this sense, former Supreme Court Justice Celso de Melo makes a serious mistake when he refers to himself and his ministerial colleagues as interpreters of *constitutional law* (*apud* Paulino, 2018), because this is not stated in any text of the Magna Carta and, from an epistemological standpoint, this idea can be considered a classic type of conventionalism.

It is becoming clear that a collegial decision at any level is, ultimately, not a constitutional decision; rather, it is the individual interpretation of a judge, the rapporteur of the case, and the majority of the court members agree with his opinion. One only needs to pay attention to the words used to clarify this fact to realize that it is not being said that this is an

infallible formula for understanding the subject matter of the judgment; hence, the assertion that the litigious status of the matter cannot be considered closed (*op.cit*).

When referring to the fact that a collegial decision of the Supreme Court cannot be understood as constitutional *verbatim* , the suspicion is not directed at the magistrates and their respective understandings of the matter itself; rather, it refers to the fact that the constitutionality of the matter has already been called into question; therefore, all that follows are arbitrary understandings, interpretations, and decisions, which become the object of agreement or disagreement by the interested parties, both now and in the future, according to their convenience.

In many situations, such representations presented to the Supreme Court are veritable traps, prepared with the sole purpose of generating doubts about the effectiveness of the document that determines the supremacy of laws in the country. And, with each piece submitted and received as a right of the people and democratic institutions to question the scope of the law, the Magna Carta is further weakened, its sovereign power is diminished, and it is transferred to the judges who then determine its scope, initially, and its validity, subsequently.

In a short time, the entire society ceases to believe in the moderating power of the Constitution, based on its legitimate sovereignty, giving rise, in place of the trust it should inspire, to a feeling of fear and distrust, because depending on who judges the action brought, the decision rendered will conform to their thinking and no longer to the written norm; that is, the arbitrator becomes the literal representation of the law. When such a level of power is reached, another, deeper risk arises: that justice will be confused with the individual decisions of this single judge; because their democratic state of mind evolves and they cease to be a literal representation of the law, but rather the literal representation of justice itself. The decision rendered by the representation submitted to their judgment is interpreted as justice having been done.

Contrary to this state of affairs, the role that the Democratic Rule of Law confers on the Judiciary is that of intervening in the elucidation of laws when they are obscure, or when both litigating parties present themselves within the right to their demands, with no possibility of reasonable understanding; however, when the law is clear, it dispenses with any type of interpretation, because its wording already delimits the legitimate dimensions that belong to each party in the process and the competence of who should judge the merits of the issue, which already determines as a bizarre effect of democracy in which, even the litigating parties having legitimate knowledge of the dimensions concerning their rights and duties [*that are incumbent upon them*], insist on moving towards the decisions offered by the courts.

The mere fact that this occurs too frequently in democratic nations, especially in Brazil, already demonstrates the population's lack of legal knowledge, coupled with the presence of bad faith regarding intentions that prioritize individual interests over public interests. It is in this epistemic context that Paulino (2018) argues that, "the legitimacy of any right established in the constitution or laws will lie in the equity of the procedures employed to resolve moral disagreements" (p. 82).

From this, it can be inferred that we are dealing with social conflicts of any kind, not referring exclusively to individual rights, which differ greatly from individual interests; a situation that, if not properly interpreted in light of the principle of reasonableness, creates the infamous judicial clientelism, in which the Judicial Court becomes enslaved to the desires of individuals or ill-intentioned groups who, instead of serving equity, in the sense of guaranteeing the preservation of the sacred principle established in the Constitution that refers to "respect for the dignity of the human person" (Brazil, 2025, p. 30), put themselves at the service of creating an anarchic State, in which its moral force is being surreptitiously undermined.

Here we are dealing with aspects related to the exercise of jurisdiction at the constitutional level, that is, within the spectrum of understanding the Public Thing as a nation and not diffuse interests, originating from interpretations of ordinary and daily life and existence. The understandings that have been adopted, at the whim of the pen, for the legitimate determinations constitutionalized by democratic power are causing the country to be immersed in such a state of corruption and demoralization that the State itself is endorsing and guaranteeing it as legitimate, because all those who have the financial means to bear the procedural expenses are carrying out their commercial activities according to the interpretation of those who have distinguished themselves and called themselves enlightened agents with sufficiently legitimate power to determine what is legitimate [*and what is not*], in accordance with the express wording in the country's Magna Carta.

A thorough understanding of constitutional law, the laws that govern the nation, and those that specifically comprise the Constitution, should represent the indisputable sovereign rule in the educational formation of a people; because, in this way, the necessary elucidation would be guaranteed so that the dignity of each citizen is not decided by the judgment of a single individual, but rather by the *cold letter of the law*¹, ensuring the application of the

¹ The *cold letter of the law* refers to the literal and exact interpretation of the text of the law, without taking into account the spirit or intention of the legislator. It is the rigorous application of the words of the law, as if they were a set of instructions without room for flexibility or subjective interpretation. In other words, it is the interpretation that adheres only to what is written in the law, without taking into account the historical, social, economic, or

principle of equality, a crucial condition for the control of constitutionality and the guarantee of law and order as the foundations of law and social justice.

The main reason for the existence of a constitutional text is to guarantee that everyone, without distinction, is protected by the law, ensuring maximum protection, especially for the most vulnerable. This is one of F. Nietzsche's main criticisms of the democratic regime, which he referred to as a government of the weak, in which the State, in its organizational capacity, castrated all men, making them eunuchs before life and, to defend them from the most rapacious and ferocious, created mechanisms [*in the form of laws and moral conduct*] that seek to equalize everyone, without distinction. When the socio-legal expression that "all are equal before the law, without distinction of any kind" is used (Brazil, [1988] 2025, art. 5, p. 14), reference is being made to constitutional jurisprudence, which is sovereign over all other forms of understanding and application of the legal scope. In this way, the aim is to preserve what has been advocated as the right to the dignity of the human person.

Extending this understanding, Dowric et al. (2025) clarify that they consider dignity to be better understood as the 'inherent and inalienable value of all human beings, regardless of social status, [...] physical or mental state'. This is not Kant's assumption that dignity can only be granted to individuals based on their rational autonomy. Dignity is, as the 1948 Declaration of Human Rights states, a universal human attribute, applied equally to those who have capacity and those who do not (Funk, Drew, Baudel , 2015; Debes , 2023; Dowric , 2025) .

The Brazilian constitutional text, promulgated in 1988, is very transparent regarding the universality of this right, which can be interpreted from the consensus that has developed as inherent to human beings—that is, a natural right, an advance in sociological thought never before conceived and applied, given the historical context of nations [*including Brazil itself*]—and which revolutionized legal-humanistic thought. However, if a text written with extensive linguistic transparency requires an interpreter, we are faced with a situation that neither Justice nor Pedagogy can solve.

Without the protection of the right to human dignity, the resulting cause is the reification of the human being, their transformation into a thing, so that they can then be used, abused, and discarded as if they were nothing. The mere fact of instituting a guardian to ensure that the law is always observed and guaranteed, *ad aeternum* , already demonstrates that this situation is a constant existence. Knowing that man tends to keep his most perverse instincts alive, because, as Gramsci (1891-1937) states, these are not destroyed, but at most tamed, and it only takes a

moral context that surrounds it. This form of interpretation can be seen as a positivist approach, which emphasizes the importance of the law as a source of law and the need for its rigorous application (Author's notes, 2025).

scratch on the veneer of civilization for the wolf's skin to be revealed in its entirety and ferocity, always attacking those who are vulnerable or who are more fragile by nature. Therefore, the purpose of the existence of law and its protector, the *Power* that never sleeps and that guarantees order while the city sleeps, is to prevent abuses, unnecessary wars, slavery, and all types of violence to which the human volitional desire to subdue one's equals, for mere morbid pleasure, is put into action whenever one feels bored or considers oneself to be in the right. Aristotle (384-322 BC) argues, in his work (*Politics* , 2007), that Heracles was a thief and could be so because he was stronger than his contemporaries; thus, he argued that those who were weaker than him should yield to his demands and whims.

In this sense, the supremacy of the exercise of constitutional courts is legitimized in the constitutional text, especially regarding the constitutionality [*or not, in this case, there is a thesis*] of the acts of the State and its federated entities, represented by the Executive Branch. This wording was implemented in the document through a Constitutional Amendment; therefore, it is not legitimized by the constituent assembly, simply because it is not circumscribed in the original legal document. When it is expressed here that this is not a legitimate action, it does not refer to the fact that everything is being handled in disregard of the law; it refers to the fact that this condition opens precedents for interpretations derived from hidden and diffuse interests of a highly personal nature, jeopardizing the democratic order, which always aims [*at least in theory, at the well-being of the majority*].

The 1988 Federal Constitution expresses itself on the matter in question as follows:

Article 97. Only by a vote of an absolute majority of its members or of the members of the respective special body may the courts declare the unconstitutionality of a law or normative act of the Public Power;

Article 102. The Supreme Federal Court is primarily responsible for safeguarding the Constitution, and its duties include:

I – to process and judge , originally:

a) direct action of unconstitutionality of a federal or state law or normative act and the declaratory action of constitutionality of a federal law or normative act;

§ 1 The Attorney General of the Republic must be heard beforehand in actions of unconstitutionality and in all proceedings within the jurisdiction of the Supreme Federal Court;

[...]

§ 3 When the Supreme Federal Court considers the unconstitutionality, in theory, of a legal norm or normative act, it shall previously summon the Attorney General of the Union, who will defend the challenged act or text (Brazil, 2025, pp. 88-96).

When the law infers that the Supreme Court is the guardian of the Constitution, this does not imply that it takes it as an object of subjective possession and legitimates itself in this sense.

The legitimate reference is to ensure that it preserves the autonomy of the laws contained therein and that everyone unconditionally respects them strictly and responsibly. It is not given the moral or legal obligation to compel citizens and entities to respect it and its principles, under penalty of becoming an instrument of tyranny. The observance of respect and obedience to the laws of a nation is a civic duty and, under any circumstances, in a democracy, can be imposed by a state body, because the laws must be so clear and transparent that there would be no need for interpretation.

The silence of republican institutions regarding these voices that self-legitimize themselves as deities interpreting the supreme law is not sufficient to grant them such power. The power of Congress [*Lower House, representing the People*] and the Senate [*Upper House, representing the Nation-State*] is legitimate, and here, a hermeneutic grounded in semantics is necessary, where this word derives from the Latin word *legis (law)*, that is, it is described *verbatim* in the Magna Carta of any nation and, in the specific case of Brazil, everything is legislated, with the magistrate being responsible for applying the law to cases and, in the case of *omissions*, where the law is not transparent enough, its clarification is due, given from their understanding, making use of the instruments of Law and a methodology that allows the application of the *principle of falsifiability*².

Former Minister Celso de Melo's statement leaves open several possible interpretations of the Brazilian Constitution, dubbed the " *Citizen Constitution* ," which is interpreted as such because, like the Brazilian citizen, it speaks nonsense; it talks about things it doesn't understand and doesn't study; or this is simply another euphemism for a document that is, in fact, completely obscure. In this sense, Paulino (2018) argues that "[...] defenders of the exercise of constitutional courts justify it because they have the possibility of focusing exclusively on individual rights, being independent of politics and bound only to the constitution and the law" (Paulino, 2018, p. 91).

This line of thinking already expresses a complete lack of understanding of human psychology and, at a deeper level, of social psychology. No matter how much someone wants to remain detached from the world's problems and interpret them in the light of laws, these laws are created by political agents who are immersed in conflicts of all kinds. A nation is formed by collectives of people, not by individuals; therefore, when immaculate individuals begin to judge individual interests, believing they are judging individual rights, what they are doing is

²Karl Popper (1902-1994) argued that science cannot be defined by the ability to verify a theory, but rather by the ability to refute it. Scientific theories are, by nature, attempts to understand reality, but they must be open to the possibility of being questioned and refuted through empirical testing (Author's notes, 2025).

condemning the nation to a possible civil war. And if anyone believes this statement to be an excessive exaggeration, one need only observe what has happened to the country's major urban centers and cities far from state control, where gangs, armed militias, and terrorist groups have all been taking absolute control over spaces, creating controlled territories in such a way that, when the State attempts to represent itself, offering the population a minimum of dignity, this action, which is a constitutional prerogative and statutory duty of the Union, is interpreted by the Supreme Court as an unconstitutional act. In other words, the very thing that should guarantee the duty on the part of the entity as a way of ensuring the full right of the citizen becomes prevented from exercising it because of an oracle. With this, the Republic deteriorates until the moment when there is no longer any kind of power, based on judgment, that can guarantee law and order, and the Constitution becomes a mere decorative figure, subject to requests for replacement by another that proves stronger and that, in some miraculous way, is respected by citizens and institutions.

The problem lies not in the Constitution itself, nor in how its laws are interpreted; it lies in the mere fact that its laws have become objects of peaceful interpretation. Anyone who disrespects the supreme law of the land, regardless of their rank, should be punished with the fullest extent of the law, and their punishment should serve as an example to others who might silently attempt to do so in any other situation, present or future. This is the purpose of a nation's Supreme Court: to be the absolute guardian of the Constitution and guarantee the constitutionality of its laws, preserving law and order so that there is neither anarchy nor tyranny.

Emile Durkheim (1858-1917) categorically stated that the social exerts power over the individual because, being more numerous, the condition of guaranteeing the continuity of the species is far superior and obvious. Therefore, overprotection towards a single being goes against the physical category of guaranteeing the preservation of the group's survival. This is an anthropological concept that extends to the sociological principle and, to Law, as an essential part of the existence of the Modern State, its guarantee is its essence, in which the essence of the Public Thing is its movement, that is, guaranteeing equality and security in an equitable manner. Following this line of reasoning, when judges operate individual rights to the detriment of the social, without considering broader issues, what we have is *judicial activism* and not the application of law according to the cause itself, and in so acting, they commit a crime against the nation.

In a democratic state, and in the case of Brazil, its constitutional determination goes beyond this, defining it as a *Democratic State of Law* . That is, it is not only a nation that is

guided by law, but that law determines it and its actions. The legitimacy of all social life and everything linked to it is given by the *cold letter of the law*; i.e., if not recorded in the records, customary law has no legal value whatsoever. All life and existence characterizing citizenship are subject to positive law. To broaden the understanding, those who are linked to Public Power, in any way, are under the principle of *positive liberty*, that is, they must rigorously and strictly follow what the law determines, leaving no room for interpretations about their conditions and actions. Therefore, when the Supreme Court justices define for themselves the role of interpreters of the Federal Constitution, they are acting under the principle of *negative liberty*, that is, as arbiters of a self-imposed condition that finds no substance in the law of the country. Thus, by acting in this way, they no longer become guardians of the Magna Carta, but its *self-legitimized* owners.

Thus, in a short time, the Nation, previously defined by democratic thought, becomes a form of dictatorship, in which individuals become afraid to express their opinions on things because they base their existence on the law that governs them; however, from some undetermined moment, this same *legal condition* proves insufficient to protect them from abuses stemming from those who have a moral and constitutional obligation to safeguard the natural right to individual liberty as a supreme good. What differentiates a dictatorship from a democracy is the feeling of security and trust the people have in their rulers, present in one and completely absent in the other.

The State, as T. Hobbes (1588-1679) stated, is the *Leviathan*, a metaphor for a monster that needs organic control; in this sense, Constitutional Courts act to ensure that the State fulfills its constitutional role of protecting its citizens and guaranteeing their full right to dignity as *individuals with rights*. Conversely, if rules begin to be dictated to all those who believe they have the right to satisfy their most intrinsic desires to the detriment of culture, tradition, and morality, then these courts exceed the legitimacy of their power and become the very monster they so fervently believe they are fighting. F. Nietzsche (2006, pp. 95-96) argues that "He who fights monsters should see to it that in the process he does not himself become a monster. And if you gaze long enough into an abyss, the abyss will gaze back into you!"

Democracy, in itself, is a regime that lives under a *Sword of Damocles*, and proof of this lies in the sanctions created and imposed on those who dare to threaten its order and existence. This is a paradox, because nowhere in the world is there a known democratic regime that exists and persists on peaceful grounds, without what has become known as political polarization. To understand this properly, the essence of human existence is characterized by fierce competition over and based on individual interests, and at most, those of one's group.

Even in countries governed by single-party systems, political polarization exists, and what seems like an absurd idea is explained by the fact that humans are political beings.

The idea that politics is done through dialogue and common sense is the purest perception that Political Science courses no longer train political scientists, but rather figures who isolate themselves from the world and who, like Plato, imagine a paradise-city where everything happens according to an ethereal order imbued with all the holy naiveté one might believe to be present in the spirit of someone arranging the logs of a bonfire that is burning an innocent person alive ³.

The control of constitutionality rests with the Constitution itself, which must contain laws so transparent that anyone who consults it can properly understand the imposed limits, thus serving the interests of managers and entrepreneurs in their initiatives and the projection of public policies. Since man tends to break treaties and the social contract, it is natural that a kind of guardian be established, so that its presence guarantees discipline and order. But in Brazil, it seems that things have happened in reverse, and the maintenance of such a state of magistrates with the mission of protecting the law has had a reverse effect on the legal framework, precisely because there is no control over the exercise of constitutionality, which is adrift, being decided according to the whims and opinions of common sense, which, in turn, has been guiding the criteria for control and determining what is constitutional and what is not regarding governance.

CONCLUSION

In a democracy, the most objective aspect of its existence and maintenance would be that all citizens of the Republic thoroughly understand its constitution and the dictates explicitly stated therein, not trusting anyone who claims to dictate it or say what is contained therein. However, Brazilians, heirs to the most bloodthirsty and imbecilic Roman Catholic tradition, just as the Church did and still does with the Bible, politicians do with the Constitution, expecting that to interpret it, an individual must be initiated into some ecclesiastical order, received under the light of wisdom. Therefore, if any document needs to be *interpreted*, it is not of human origin, it is an oracle and, according to contemporary social norms, it is useless.

³ *Oh, sancta simplicitas!* (Oh, holy ingenuity!) It was, according to the text, the last sentence uttered by Jan Hus (1369-1415), when he was in the martyrdom of the Hoguera, where he was condemned for heresy, and he remained in a life, moved by his religious cell, he threw more fire to the calls where that fire burned (<http://www.jeanpauldemoule.com/livre-blanc-ce-nest-quun-debut/>).

A country's constitution and all its legal and moral norms fall under the *cold letter of the law*, and must be transparent, objective, and direct, dispensing with intermediaries who seek to give it the meaning that best suits them. The mere fact that someone petitions the Supreme Court seeking an *interpretation* of the constitutional legal text should already be considered a crime against the Constitution, and the judges should deny the request without any right to consider the merits of the representation itself.

This right [*which has become an obligation of the Supreme Court*] that it is the interpreter of constitutional laws is a power that has been granted to magistrates by common sense in the most faithful use of public bad faith against the principles of the Nation. Worse than this are the amendments to the Constitution that this attitude provokes, transforming the document into a source of political and legal instability, in which lobbyists work to convince legislators that the wording of a certain law should be in the way they deem best, not because it will favor the *public*; but because the way it is intended to be becomes clear, understandable, and comprehensive. All this discourse is nothing more than euphemism, because the changes, as well as the original text, remain unknown to the great mass.

Nowhere in the law is it written or described that the Supreme Court must act as an oracle of the Federal Constitution; therefore, this category attributed to it is not, in itself, legitimate. And, when one defends the *literal application* of the law circumscribed in the Magna Carta, disregarding the entire context in which it applies and, especially, the subjectivity of the judge, there are two conflicting points, the first being that, when the constituent assembly drafted the set of rules and compiled them in the code, it did so considering the entire set of sociological influences of its time, leaving room for the rules to be discussed *and* the necessary interventions carried out in order to [*always*] serve the social well-being, in situations of broadening of thought and scientific development.

Changes to constitutional norms are extremely delicate legal and social matters, requiring a study of the advances and changes resulting from technical development, population growth, and scientific and technological advancements, while simultaneously examining the scope of existing laws to determine if they already address such occurrences, thus not limiting the processes of creation and innovation in the various fields of knowledge.

The way decisions regarding the constitutionality of events and government decisions have been promoted in Brazil creates, by extension [*and through a lack of reason and sensitivity*], legal uncertainty that only serves to drive away international investors and national entrepreneurs. The State itself becomes enslaved by an instability that, little by little, transforms into a *Sword of Damocles* hanging over the head of the manager.

When a Supreme Court justice states that their role is to be an interpreter [*an oracle*] of a nation's Constitution, they create, from the outset, the possibility of treating the document as *impossible* for normal human beings to understand. This makes the members of the Court indispensable consultants on any and all matters, even those in which they have no knowledge whatsoever. Following this legal uncertainty, groups that live solely to cause disorder and obstruct the governmental administrative process take advantage of the situation and begin to interfere in all kinds of government through those appointed with the obligation to foster the socio-political advancement of the nation, through the strict promotion of the necessary conditions for the promotion of jurisprudential security.

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